

Delivering the next generation of open Integrated Assessment MOdels for Net-zero, sustainable Development

D3.1 – MODEL DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY

WP3 – Update & Upgrade

30/03/2023

Funded by
the European Union

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Copyright Message

This report, if not confidential, is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0); a copy is available here: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>. You are free to share (copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format) and adapt (remix, transform, and build upon the material for any purpose, even commercially) under the following terms: (i) attribution (you must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made; you may do so in any reasonable manner, but not in any way that suggests the licensor endorses you or your use); (ii) no additional restrictions (you may not apply legal terms or technological measures that legally restrict others from doing anything the license permits).

Grant Agreement Number	101081179		Acronym	DIAMOND
Full Title	Delivering the next generation of open Integrated Assessment MODEls for Net-zero, sustainable Development			
Topic	HORIZON-CL5-2022-D1-02			
Funding scheme	HORIZON EUROPE, RIA – Research and Innovation Action			
Start Date	December 2022	Duration	48 Months	
Project URL	http://www.climate-diamond.eu/			
EU Project Advisor	Silvia Vaghi			
Project Coordinator	Institute of Communications and Computer Systems - ICCS			
Deliverable	D3.1 – Model development strategy			
Work Package	WP3 – Update & Upgrade			
Date of Delivery	Contractual	24/03/2023	Actual	31/03/2023
Nature	Report	Dissemination	Public	
Lead Beneficiary	Asociacion BC3 Basque Centre for Climate Change - Klima Aldaketa Ikergai (BC3)			
Responsible Author	Jon Sampedro (BC3)	Email	jon.sampedro@bc3research.org	
	BC3	Phone	+34 94 401 46 90 (Ext) 136	
Contributors	Dirk-Jan Van de Ven (BC3); Gabriele Cassetti, Maurizio Gargiulo (E4SMA); Constantinos Taliotis (CYI); Marc Vielle, Sigit Perdana (EPFL); Baptiste Boitier (SEURECO); Anastasis Giannousakis, Panagiotis Fragkos (E3M)			
Reviewer(s)	Shivika Mittal, Georgios Xexakis, Konstantinos Koasidis, Constantinos Taliotis			
Keywords	Integrated assessment; Model development; Climate policy; Sustainability			

EC Summary Requirements

1. Changes with respect to the DoA

No changes with respect to the work described in the DoA.

2. Dissemination and uptake

The deliverable is intended for policymakers and the broader stakeholder community of DIAMOND and other IAM-related projects to showcase the capabilities and simple descriptions of the models in the armoury of the project. It is also intended for the scientific community of IAMs to present the added capabilities, expansions, and integrations that are performed in DIAMOND.

3. Short summary of results (<250 words)

Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) have historically been the dominant tools in climate policy assessment and the analysis of the implications of alternative global and/or regional scenarios. In DIAMOND, a coordinated effort will be undertaken to update, upgrade, expand, and integrate six different sector-wide IAMs. This deliverable first outlines generally perceived limitations of such models, and how interaction with stakeholders in the development process is important to improve the policy relevance of their outputs. To do so, an overview and a perceived model development plan within DIAMOND is provided for each model. This information has been gathered through a harmonised survey that was filled by all modelling teams and attached to this deliverable. The outputs of the survey show that all models plan to expand in both geographical and sectoral/technological coverage. Three out of six models (GCAM-Europe, CLEWs-EU, and OPEN-PROM) aim to represent the European Union (EU) by individual member states, while two other models (GEMINI-E3-EU and OMNIA) to make progress in the geographical detail in the EU as well. Three models (NEMESIS-World, OPEN-PROM, and OMNIA) are expanding coverage in the rest of the world. In terms of technological coverage, development strategies are also heterogeneous, but with clear priorities for an improved representation of hydrogen technologies in all six models of the DIAMOND project as well as electricity storage technologies in four of the models. In terms of policy representation, a large part of newly developed representation will be focusing on trade policies, while all models will also be improved in terms of implementation of behavioural measures.

4. Evidence of accomplishment

This report and the corresponding Zenodo dataset (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7774836>) including the surveys for all models.

Preface

DIAMOND will update, upgrade, and fully open six Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) that are emblematic in scientific and policy processes, improving their sectoral and technological detail, spatiotemporal resolution, and geographic granularity. It will further enhance modelling capacity to assess the feasibility and desirability of Paris-compliant mitigation pathways, their interplay with adaptation, circular economy, and other SDGs, their distributional and equity effects, and their resilience to extremes, as well as robust risk management and investment strategies. This will be done via integration of tools and insights from psychology, finance research, behavioural and labour economics, operational research, and physical science. The project will develop a transdisciplinary scientific approach to legitimise the implementation process and co-create research questions that stretch the frontiers of climate science, as well as establish vibrant communities of practice to transparently open model enhancements and to develop capacities, thereby lowering the entrance barriers to the established IAM community.

ICCS	INSTITUTE OF COMMUNICATIONS AND COMPUTER SYSTEMS	EL	
BC3	ASOCIACION BC3 BASQUE CENTRE FOR CLIMATE CHANGE - KLIMA ALDAKETA IKERGAI	ES	
CESAR	KRATENA KURT	AT	
CICERO	CICERO CENTER FOR KLIMAFORSKNING	NO	
CYI	THE CYPRUS INSTITUTE	CY	
E4SMA	ENERGY ENGINEERING ECONOMIC ENVIRONMENT SYSTEMS MODELING AND ANALYSIS SRL	IT	
HOLISTIC	HOLISTIC IKE	EL	
COMILLAS	UNIVERSIDAD PONTIFICIA COMILLAS	ES	
ISINNOVA	ISTITUTO DI STUDI PER L'INTEGRAZIONE DEI SISTEMI (I.S.I.S) - SOCIETA'COOPERATIVA	IT	
SEURECO	SEURECO SOCIETE EUROPEENNE D'ECONOMIE SARL	FR	
UM	UNIVERSITEIT MAASTRICHT	NL	
ESMIA	ESMIA CONSULTANTS INC.	CA	
USMF	THE UNIVERSITY OF MARYLAND FOUNDATION INC	US	
UMD	UNIVERSITY SYSTEM OF MARYLAND	US	
EPFL	ECOLE POLYTECHNIQUE FEDERALE DE LAUSANNE	CH	
ETH	EIDGENOESSISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE ZUERICH	CH	
UNIBAS	UNIVERSITAT BASEL	CH	
Imperial	IMPERIAL COLLEGE OF SCIENCE TECHNOLOGY AND MEDICINE	UK	
Oxford	THE CHANCELLOR, MASTERS AND SCHOLARS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF OXFORD	UK	
UCL	UNIVERSITY COLLEGE LONDON	UK	

Executive Summary

Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) have historically been the dominant tools in climate policy assessment and the analysis of global and/or regional scenarios. While these models have largely contributed to global and regional policymaking and climate change mitigation strategies, scientific literature has pointed out some weaknesses or areas of improvement that should be considered for the robustness of future IAM applications. One of the main critiques to IAMs is that they do not represent socioeconomic and political barriers associated with the implementation of alternative policies. Another critique of IAMs is the misrepresentation of certain dynamics that can lead to a misinterpretation of derived outcomes, such as the common practice to use economy-wide carbon prices as an oversimplified proxy for global climate policies. One of the main aspects to be improved is achieving finer temporal and geographical scales to assess distinct region/country specific solution space. Finally, another area of improvement for IAMs is the lack of transparency and detailed documentation. IAMs have frequently been considered as “black boxes”, with opaque input assumptions that do not allow a full understanding of the uncertainties embedded in the produced outputs. This model development plan lays out the core model improvement activities in DIAMOND in order to improve six multi-sectoral IAMs, ensuring open-access, transparency, and the ability to address the most relevant research questions from different stakeholders and policymakers at different scales.

The first step is the preparation of an initial development plan. The six IAMs within DIAMOND have different modelling structures, including the geographical, temporal, and sectoral coverage, the representation of the different variables and policy mechanisms, the input requirements, or the solver algorithm. We have created a survey that gathers the main features of each model, e.g., regional, sectoral and technological coverage, as well as scenario/policy-specific information such as implementable policies and mitigation measures. The survey highlights which features were already represented in the models, and which will be developed within DIAMOND. This information is crucial to collect and incorporate stakeholder inputs (WP2) on how model development can meet their needs, which will be an important input for the final model development plans. Also, this information helps to establish the collaboration between WP3 modelling teams and sectoral modules in WP4, which depends on the model structures, as well as the sectoral and technological coverage in models. Finally, information on coverage of policy types and mitigation measures for explorative scenarios in WP5 is provided.

The outputs of the survey show that all models plan to expand in both geographical and sectoral/technological coverage. Three out of six models (GCAM-Europe, CLEWs-EU, and OPEN-PROM) aim to represent the European Union (EU) by individual member states, while two other models (GEMINI-E3-EU and OMNIA) will improve the disaggregation by splitting the EU in more regions, making them able to represent EU policies and targets in more detail. Three models (NEMESIS-World, OPEN-PROM, and OMNIA) are expanding coverage in the rest of the world, separating out major regions for more detailed mitigation scenario analysis. In terms of technological coverage, development strategies are also heterogeneous, but with clear priorities for an improved representation of hydrogen technologies (all 6 models) and electricity storage technologies (4 models). In terms of policy representation, a large part of newly developed representation will be focusing on trade policies (potentially being covered by all models—only 2 models originally covered them), while all models will implement behavioural measures, whereas originally only two models were able to do so.

Contents

1 INTRODUCTION	1
2 METHODOLOGY	3
3 MODEL DEVELOPMENT STRATEGIES	5
3.1 From GCAM to GCAM-Europe.....	5
3.2 From TIAM to OMNIA	8
3.3 From CLEWs to CLEWs-EU.....	11
3.4 From GEMINI-E3 to GEMINI-E3 EU	14
3.5 From NEMESIS to NEMESIS-World	17
3.6 From PROMETHEUS to OPEN-PROM	20
3.7 Interconnections with other models	23
3.8 Policies and measures.....	24
Bibliography	27
ANNEX	32

Table of Figures

Figure 1. Regional disaggregation in GCAM-Europe.....	6
Figure 2. Summary of the resource, technology, and end-use demand representation in GCAM-Europe.	7
Figure 3. Regional disaggregation in OMNIA.	8
Figure 4. Summary of the resource, technology, and end-use demand representation in OMNIA.	10
Figure 5. Regional disaggregation in CLEWS-EU.	11
Figure 6. Summary of the resource, technology, and end-use demand representation in CLEWS-EU.	13
Figure 7. Regional disaggregation in GEMINI-E3 EU.....	15
Figure 8. Summary of the resource, technology, and end-use demand representation in GEMINI-E3-EU.....	16
Figure 9. Regional disaggregation in NEMESIS-World	18
Figure 10. Summary of the resource, technology, and end-use demand representation in NEMESIS-World.....	19
Figure 11. Regional disaggregation in OPEN-PROM.	21
Figure 12. Summary of the resource, technology, and end-use demand representation in OPEN-PROM.	22

Table of Tables

Table 1. Overview of the survey contents.....	3
Table 2. Summary of model developments	5
Table 3. Summary of the planned inter-model connections associated with WP4.....	24
Table 4. Overview of the climate policies represented in each model.	24
Table 5. Overview of the energy, land and end-use demand measures represented in each model.	25

1 INTRODUCTION

Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) have historically been the dominant tools in climate policy assessment and the analysis of the implications of alternative global and/or regional scenarios (van Beek et al., 2020). These models are designed to explore alternative “what if”-type scenarios and to evaluate the interdependencies between the economy, energy, agriculture, forestry, and land use (AFOLU), water or climate systems. Due to their flexibility, they have been largely used in several global and regional scenario analyses and policymaking. Some representative examples are the scenarios within the different assessment reports by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) (IPCC, 2022), the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) (O’Neill et al., 2014), or the U.S. strategy to reach net zero emissions in 2050 (Horowitz et al., 2022).

While these models have largely contributed to global and regional policymaking and climate change mitigation strategies (Weyant, 2017), scientific literature has pointed out some weaknesses or areas of improvement that should be considered for the robustness of future IAM applications. One of the main critiques to IAMs is the fact that they do not represent socioeconomic and political barriers that different policymakers face for the implementation of the alternative policies (Peng et al., 2021). The engagement of different stakeholders for scenario development and policy analysis has become essential for the trustfulness and social acceptance of IAM results (Miller & Wyborn, 2020). In addition, recent literature has demonstrated the importance of incorporating the views of a wide range of stakeholders at different levels, including international experts, cross-regional organisations, national governments, regional institutions, local agents, and citizens (Galende-Sánchez & Sorman, 2021). While IAM modellers use stakeholder inputs to better represent certain model parameters or dynamics, they have only recently started to be in the scenario design (Nikas et al., 2023). The co-creation and co-production of alternative scenarios, taking onboard collective stakeholder insights, is an active research line for the IAM community in order to produce results that are more meaningful and socially relevant. In addition, stakeholder information will be key to identify model weaknesses and potential improvements.

Another critique for IAMs is the misrepresentation of certain dynamics that can drive to a misinterpretation of the produced outcomes. For example, some studies conclude that the implementation of global climate policies in IAMs are usually oversimplified (Keppo et al., 2021). The use of a universal carbon price is a common assumption, which does not represent real world policies (Sognaes et al., 2021). Similarly, IAMs do not model the finance system or the capital markets. The perception of different investors (e.g., banks or funds) will play an essential role in the energy transition that needs to be considered to project alternative socioeconomic and/or technological pathways (Battiston et al., 2021). More broadly, different studies have highlighted that the way of representing the epistemic and structural uncertainties can lead to misinterpretations of the model results (Beck & Krueger, 2016; Pindyck, 2017).

One of the main aspects to be improved is the need to move to finer temporal and geographical scales. The improvement of both temporal and geographical coverage has become a priority for the IAM community (Mulugetta et al., 2022; Peng et al., 2021), since a more detailed granularity is needed to better inform the policy debate. Historically, IAMs work at year or multi-year time-steps (i.e., 5-year periods). This implies that the models do not capture within-year dynamics (e.g., disruptive events or seasonality), that may be particularly relevant for some sectors, such as the power sector (Wise et al., 2019). Furthermore, IAMs do not incorporate within-region inequality considerations to capture the contribution of different socioeconomic groups to global warming, or the impacts of global change to the different groups within each region, which is becoming essential for the design and assessment of the decarbonization strategies

(Sampedro, 2021; UNFCCC, 2016). **This is a top priority for the IAM community, with several studies demanding for these inequality considerations for climate policy assessment** (Emmerling & Tavoni, 2021; Rao et al., 2017). **While some studies are emerging in this line** (Dagnachew et al., 2020; Pobleto-Cazenave et al., 2021; Sampedro et al., 2022; Van Ruijven et al., 2015), **this feature is not systematically incorporated into the models.**

Finally, another area of improvement for IAMs is the lack of transparency and detailed documentation. IAMs have frequently been considered as “black-boxes”, with opaque input assumptions that do not allow a full understanding of the uncertainties embedded in the produced outputs (Pindyck, 2013; Van der Sluijs, 2002). **Likewise, the lack of peer review for these models can reduce their credibility** (Rosen, 2015). **Increasing model transparency has become a high priority for the IAM community, particularly for improving the reliability of the scenarios analysed in the IPCC reports** (Robertson, 2021; Skea et al., 2021). **Recent multi-model intercomparison studies have emphasized the need for comparing modelling assumptions, in order to reduce the heterogeneity of model responses** (Giarola et al., 2021; Krey et al., 2019). **Similarly, the IAMC community is actively promoting different open-access tools to explore the alternative IPCC scenarios and improve their transparency and re-use, such as the AR6 scenario explorer** (Byers et al., 2022), **the 1.5°C scenario explorer** (Huppmann et al., 2018), **the *pyam* package** (Gidden & Huppmann, 2019), **or the I2AM PARIS platform** (Nikas et al., 2021). **Nevertheless, improving the documentation of model input parameters, assumptions, and uncertainties becomes essential for improving the relevance and acceptance of model results.**

One of the main objectives of DIAMOND is to update and expand existing IAMs, incorporating stakeholder information and the potential interconnection with bottom-up sectoral models, in order to overcome existing limitations and make sure that the outcomes produced will be robust, trustful, and socially relevant. In this deliverable, we will present a strategy to coordinate the model development activities in DIAMOND in order to improve six multi-sectoral IAMs, assuring open-access, transparency, and the ability to address the most relevant research questions for different stakeholders and policymakers at different scales.

2 METHODOLOGY

The main objective of this task is to develop a common model development strategy to improve the capabilities and the political and social relevance of the existing global IAMs [Work Package (WP) 3], and connect them with sectoral models (WP4) to widen the scope of the potential research questions they can analyse (WP5).

The first step is the preparation of the **initial development plan**. The six IAMs within DIAMOND have different modelling structures, including geographical, temporal, and sectoral coverage, the representation of different variables (exogenous or endogenous), input requirements, the implementation of policy mechanisms, or solver methods/algorithms. Therefore, we needed a common documentation space that gathers the main information about the six different models. Each modelling team will prepare a preliminary model development strategy (MS5) that will describe: 1) the refinement of the geographical and temporal scales (e.g., more detailed regional disaggregation); 2) the planned improvements in terms of dynamics, capabilities, or sectoral coverage, as well as the potential actions to improve transparency (e.g., improving the documentation or opening the source-code under an appropriate open source license); and 3) the potential interconnections with the additional sectoral models within the DIAMOND consortium. For that purpose, **we have created a survey that gathers the main features of each model** in terms of regional coverage, resource and technology representation, the end-use demands and demand drivers, the socioeconomic structure, the (lack of) incorporation of different climate feedbacks, the way of implementing alternative climate policies, or broader policy mechanisms (see **Error! Reference source not found.**). The survey also includes data sources for different input assumptions that are read in by the different models. This common documentation space facilitates the communication between the global and sectoral modelling teams in an efficient way, ensuring that all the teams take advantage of the possibilities that will emerge during the model development efforts. Furthermore, the addition of data sources used by the different models into the survey will be a co-benefit for the update and upgrade of the IAMs: each team will be able to use the data sources originally intended for the rest of the models to develop new modelling capabilities that were not originally captured in their plans. In addition, putting together all the different data sources will help towards potential harmonisation of data across different models, which will be useful for high-impact, model intercomparison studies as they can provide robust insights for alternative scenario analysis (Guivarch et al., 2022). **See the Annex for the filled surveys of all models**, which include the data sources used for every feature in those models.

Table 1. Overview of the survey contents

Sheet	Description
Model Info	Model general information and short description
Integration & Expansion	Possible links with WP4 modules and their objectives
Regions	List of the model regions and geographical aggregations
Sources & Potential	List of fossil fuels resources and renewable potentials, including the modelling function
Technologies	List of technologies included in the model and preferred data source
Demand drivers	List of energy demands, including units and demand drivers

Sheet	Description
Socio-Economics & Prices	List of endogenous/exogenous socio-economic parameters, including energy prices, used by the model
Emissions	List of endogenous/exogenous emissions
Policies	List of policies that can be modelled
Measures	List of endogenous/exogenous measures that can be modelled
Climate Impacts	List of endogenous/exogenous climate impacts covered by the model

To incorporate stakeholder insights into each model in an effective and efficient way (based on input from WP2 tasks), the modelling teams will need to:

- Identify the research questions that stakeholders want to address
- Discuss how the models can be applied for supporting policymakers in the design and assessment of different policy packages
- Use stakeholder information to identify the most crucial aspects to be improved, including:
 - Geographical and temporal scales
 - Sectoral coverage
 - Input information and assumptions
 - Misrepresented dynamics and uncertainties
 - Potential interconnection with additional sectoral models (to widen the modelling scope)

More details on the stakeholder engagement strategies can be found in the different Tasks in WP2, concretely in Task 2.1 (*"Developing an innovative stakeholder engagement plan"*), Task 2.2 (*"Phase 1 – Towards mutual understanding"*), and Task 2.3 (*"Phase 2 – Towards knowledge co-production"*).

Regarding the timeline, each modelling team is expected to start the development of the model enhancements in Month 4 (M4), as indicated in the description of WP3. Likewise, the exploration of potential interconnection options with additional bottom-up models (WP4) for some research areas (e.g., representation of labour/finance dynamics) starts at the very early stages of the project (M1). Therefore, modelling teams will need to start their model enhancement and expansion activities based on the initial development plan but will also need to be flexible to incorporate stakeholder insights and suggestions during the course of the project to ensure the models will capture their needs and will be relevant for policymaking.

3 MODEL DEVELOPMENT STRATEGIES

The six different modelling teams will follow the protocol described in the previous subsection to update, upgrade, expand, and integrate their models. The following table summarizes the planned developments, and the following subsections detail the strategies or the six global models in the consortium.

Table 2. Summary of model developments

Original model	New model	Model type
GCAM	GCAM-Europe	Partial equilibrium
TIAM	OMNIA	Partial equilibrium
Global CLEWS/GLUCOSE	CLEWS-EU	Linear optimization
GEMINI-E3	GEMINI-E3 EU	Computable general equilibrium (CGE)
NEMESIS	NEMESIS-World	Macroeconomic/Econometric
PROMETHEUS	OPEN-PROM	Partial equilibrium

3.1 From GCAM to GCAM-Europe

GCAM is a dynamic-recursive model with technology-rich representations of the economy, energy sector, land use and water linked to a climate model that can be used to explore climate change mitigation policies including carbon taxes, carbon trading, regulations and accelerated deployment of energy technology. Regional population and labour productivity growth assumptions drive the energy, land-use and water systems employing numerous technology options to produce, transform, and provide energy services as well as to produce agricultural and forest products, and to determine land use and land cover. The model has been used to explore the potential role of emerging energy supply technologies and the impact on greenhouse gas emissions of specific policy measures or energy technology adoption including; carbon dioxide (CO₂) capture and storage, bioenergy, hydrogen systems, nuclear energy, renewable energy technology, and energy demand in buildings, industry and the transportation sectors. Outputs of the model include projections of future energy supply and demand and the resulting greenhouse gas emissions, radiative forcing and climate effects of 16 greenhouse gases, aerosols and short-lived species, implications for future land cover and water use, contingent on assumptions about future population, economy, technology, and climate mitigation policy. Through separate modules, results in terms of emissions and water use can be used to estimate pre-mature mortality and water shortages by region.

For the development of GCAM-Europe, first we will add more details to the geographical disaggregation. GCAM divides the world in 32 regions, and the European continent is divided in five different regions: EU-12, EU-15, Europe Eastern, Europe-non-EU, and European Free Trade Association (EFTA). In GCAM-Europe, we will disaggregate all EU member states and key non-EU countries (e.g., UK, or Norway). Having this level of detail will enable us to explore the country-level effects of European policy packages or transformational strategies, as well as the potential international effects (e.g., carbon leakage) for a representative set of regions (27) over the world. The 59 regions disaggregated in GCAM-Europe can be found in **Error! Reference source not found.**, with the envisaged separated regions in Europe highlighted.

Figure 1. Regional disaggregation in GCAM-Europe.

Yellow-to-red colours represent the regional groups that are explicitly disaggregated for this model. White-to-blue regions represent model regional groups that were part of the original model.

The larger amount of data availability at European level will also allow GCAM-Europe to have a more detailed representation of the energy system (see **Error! Reference source not found.**). For example, hydropower represents around 17% of EU's electricity in 2020 (Eurostat) but is currently not represented in the original model. Drawing from ongoing efforts to feature endogenous hydropower generation at the global water basin level (Zhang et al., 2022), this feature will be introduced in the European version of the model as well, in coordination with the core GCAM, where it will compete with other power generation technologies based on the costs and resource potential. Likewise, hydropower generation will be connected with the water module of the model, which tracks the detailed water withdrawals and consumption for different regions and sectors at basin level. Moreover, GCAM-Europe will include different technologies for electricity storage, including batteries and hydroelectric pumped-storage, connected with the enhanced hydropower module. According to the European Commission (EC), electricity storage will play a key role in the transition towards a carbon-neutral economy, so capturing the storage dynamics is an essential development for GCAM-Europe. Another relevant improvement is the sectoral disaggregation within the residential sector. While the core model version, due to the lack of harmonized data, disaggregates the residential sector into "heating", "cooling", and "others" (non-thermal), in GCAM-Europe, we will make use of existing data to disaggregate additional sectors, namely, "hot water", "cooking", "lighting", or "appliances", in line with the US-version of the model (GCAM-USA; Binsted et al., 2021).

Figure 2. Summary of the resource, technology, and end-use demand representation in GCAM-Europe.

White boxes indicate features already part of the original model. Grey boxes indicate features not part of the core nor the updated model. Dark yellow boxes indicate the features that will be explicitly developed for GCAM-Europe in the DIAMOND project, and which are not in the core version of the model

3.2 From TIAM to OMNIA

TIMES is a modelling platform for local, national or multi-regional energy systems, which provides a technology-rich basis for estimating how energy system operations will evolve over a long-term, multiple-period time horizon (Loulou & Labriet, 2007). These energy system operations include the extraction of primary energy such as fossil fuels, the conversion of this primary energy into useful forms (such as electricity, hydrogen, solid heating fuels and liquid transport fuels), and the use of these fuels in a range of energy service applications (vehicular transport, building heating and cooling, and the powering of industrial manufacturing plants). In multi-region versions of the model, fuel trading between regions is also estimated. The TIMES framework is usually applied to the analysis of the entire energy sector but may also be applied to the detailed study of single sectors (e.g., the electricity and district heat sector). The framework can also be used to simulate the mitigation of non-CO₂ greenhouse gases, including methane (CH₄) and nitrous oxide (N₂O). The TIMES Integrated Assessment Model, TIAM, is the multi-region, global version of TIMES, which combines an energy system representation of different regions with options to mitigate non-CO₂ greenhouse gases as well as non-energy CO₂ mitigation options, such as afforestation in each of these regions. It uses emissions from these sources to calculate temperature changes using a simple climate module. As such, it can be used to explore a variety of questions on how to mitigate climate change through energy system transformations, as well as reductions in non-energy CO₂ emissions and non-CO₂ emissions.

Starting from the current version of TIAM, OMNIA will integrate several advancements to perform detailed regional analysis. Regional representation will be expanded from the current 15 regions to 31 regions (see **Error! Reference source not found.**). It will rely on up-to-date technology datasets and include additional technologies for credible policy analysis. Key technologies to decarbonise hard-to-abate sectors will be comprehensively represented (see **Error! Reference source not found.**). Industry representation will be strongly reorganised and enhanced based on ongoing research. The upstream sector, including fossil fuel extraction, will be improved to fully explore the implications of the transition. OMNIA will also incorporate a spatially explicit representation of key energy carrier trades, including bioenergy, hydrogen, as well as commodities including captured CO₂.

Figure 3. Regional disaggregation in OMNIA.

Yellow-to-red colours represent the regional groups that are explicitly disaggregated for this model. White-to-blue regions represent model regional groups that were part of the original model.

Temporal representation of energy demand and supply will be significantly increased to properly model the

increased penetration of variable renewable energy technologies, storage, and new demand technologies, expanding the time slices to 20. OMNIA will also integrate and update the TIAM climate module to estimate global average temperature changes of scenarios and include abatement supply-cost curves for all major non-CO₂ options. In addition, with a newly calibrated and improved water module, the model will be able to evaluate the interdependence between energy production and water consumption.

Figure 4. Summary of the resource, technology, and end-use demand representation in OMNIA.

White boxes indicate features already part of the original model. Grey boxes indicate features not part of the core nor the updated model. Dark yellow boxes indicate the features that will be explicitly developed for OMNIA in the DIAMOND project, and which are not in the core version of the model.

3.3 From CLEWs to CLEWs-EU

Climate, Land, Energy and Water Systems (CLEWs) is a Nexus modelling framework for integrated assessment of resource systems and of interlinkages among energy, water, and agricultural systems as well as their impacts on—and vulnerability to—climate change (e.g., food, energy, and water security). It builds on the OSeMOSYS energy modelling framework and has been further advanced for global-level, user-friendly, exploratory analysis in GLUCOSE (Global CLEWs model). This Global CLEWs model will be used as a conceptual base for the development of a CLEWs-EU model. Hence, the CLEWs-EU model will essentially be populated with relevant data from scratch. A key advantage of the CLEWs model lies in its openness and accessibility to policy and research teams all over the world, which has been maximised in capacity building activities by the United Nations (UN) Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA), the UN Development Programme (UNDP) and the UN Economic Commission for Africa (UNECA), with the UN Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE) transboundary nexus applications notably standing out as successful examples of nexus assessments to inform complex intersectoral policy dialogues. This has helped to establish a vibrant and active community of practice across the globe, throughout all stages of model development, validation, and use to inform policy. DIAMOND will build on the already open nature of CLEWs, as well as on the large community of practice in both the modelling research community and the policy world, to develop CLEWs-EU. An additional, low-complexity implementation will be built and provided for capacity development.

Building on the structure of the Global CLEWs model (Beltramo et al., 2021), several model enhancements will be accomplished within DIAMOND, in terms of both structure and content. The model will continue to be developed within the OSeMOSYS modelling framework (Howells et al., 2011) due to its open-source nature. Several model enhancements are envisioned. As a first step, an aggregated CLEWs-EU regional model will be pursued (see **Error! Reference source not found.**), in which the EU will be represented as a single node, serving as an engagement model upon which capacity development activities on EU climate policy can be developed due to its simplified structure and low computational effort.

Figure 5. Regional disaggregation in CLEWs-EU.

Yellow-to-red colours represent the regional groups that are explicitly disaggregated for this model.

Coupled with the adoption of a user-friendly interface, enabling direct changes in model parameters and visualisation of the system dynamics, it will allow the exploration of climate change mitigation pathways by a

broad range of stakeholders. This will ensure consistency with the philosophy behind the initial development of the Global CLEWs model. Secondly, a more detailed temporal resolution will be adopted; from a current annual resolution of three time-steps (day, night, and peak), years will be further broken down to at least 12 time-steps, consisting of three seasons (winter, summer, intermediate) and four typical day-parts within each season to capture both peaks in demand, as well as variability in renewable energy availability.

Furthermore, enhancements will be pursued in technological representation to increase the number of options that can render net-zero emission pathways technically feasible (see **Error! Reference source not found.**). As an essential feature, hydrogen energy chains, currently missing from the model, will be added to the energy sector module. This will subsequently change the fuel mix available to the materials production module. Additionally, splitting mobility into short- and long-term distance travel will enable the assessment of potential lifestyle changes and modal shifts—for instance, to investigate a shift from privately-owned vehicles to public transport for short-distance travel, as well as shift from air- to rail-travel for longer distances. Finally, adopting all the aforementioned enhancements, development of a CLEWs-EU disaggregated model will be carried out. The level of spatial resolution in this disaggregated model will extend to the national level, to be used for more extensive, frontiers-stretching analyses foreseen within DIAMOND.

Figure 6. Summary of the resource, technology, and end-use demand representation in CLEWS-EU.

White boxes indicate features already part of the original model. Grey boxes indicate features not part of the core nor the updated model. Dark yellow boxes indicate the features that will be, and light-yellow boxes features that might be (still to be decided), explicitly developed for CLEWS-EU in the DIAMOND project, and which are not in the core version of the model.

3.4 From GEMINI-E3 to GEMINI-E3 EU

GEMINI-E3 is a multi-country, multi-sector, recursive computable general equilibrium (CGE) model. It simulates all relevant markets, domestic and international, considered as perfectly competitive, which implies that the corresponding prices are flexible in markets for commodities (through relative prices), for labour (through wages), and for domestic and international savings (through rates of interest and exchange rates). Time periods are linked in the model through endogenous real rates of interest determined through the balancing of savings and investment. Countries and regions in GEMINI-E3 are linked by endogenous real exchange rates resulting from constraints on foreign trade deficits or surpluses. There is one notable—and usual—exception to this general assumption of perfect competition, which concerns foreign trade. Goods of the same sector produced by different countries are not supposed to be perfectly competitive; they are considered as economically different goods, more or less substitute according to an elasticity of substitution known as the Armington assumption. The main outputs of the GEMINI-E3 model are on a country and annual basis and include: carbon taxes, marginal abatement costs and prices of tradable permits (when relevant), effective abatement of CO₂ emissions, net sales of tradable permits (when relevant), total net welfare loss and components (net loss from terms of trade, pure deadweight loss of taxation, and net purchases of tradable permits when relevant), macro-economic aggregates (e.g. production, imports and final demand), real exchange rates and real interest rates, and data at the industrial level (e.g. change in production and in factors of production, and prices of goods).

The development of the new version of GEMINI-E3 aims to improve the granularity and empirical consistency of the model. First, the databases will be updated, mainly from the upgraded GTAP and GTAP Power versions. Updating other economic sources such as transfer, taxes, and other macro indicators is based on various sources such as IMF, IEA, and OECD. Second, GHG emissions coverage will be expanded to include local air pollutants. This expansion contributes to a more comprehensive assessment of the ancillary benefits of mitigation policies in standard CGE modelling. Integration of air pollutants in the new version of the model is based on the development of the air pollution database for GTAP that covers emissions for nine substances.

The last development is through regional and sectoral reclassifications. The former EU 27+UK regions will be divided into nine individual countries (including the UK) and 14 aggregated regions (see **Error! Reference source not found.**). This reclassification is based on historical data evaluation and statistical analysis. There will be 22 countries/ regions represented in the new version of the model. We will use the same approach for sectoral reclassification by focusing on essential sectors in climate economics while keeping concordance with IPCC classification and its reporting standard. This includes the Emissions Trading Scheme (ETS) that covers electricity generation, energy-intensive industries (EII), petroleum production, and the newly added aviation sector. In the original version, fossil fuels are represented by coal, oil (petroleum as its product), and natural gas sectors following the IPCC. Natural gas distribution is defined as a separate sector to distinguish between gas-producing and importing countries. Hydrogen will be introduced as part of energy sectors, along with the better representation of bioenergy (biomass and biofuel) (see **Error! Reference source not found.**). Manufacture group will also be reclassified based on the IPCC classification of manufacturing industries in line with the International Standard Industrial Classification of All Economic Activities (ISIC) Vol. 4 (United Nations, 2008).

Figure 7. Regional disaggregation in GEMINI-E3 EU.

Yellow-to-red colours represent the regional groups that are explicitly disaggregated for this model. White-to-blue regions represent model regional groups that were part of the original model.

Figure 8. Summary of the resource, technology, and end-use demand representation in GEMINI-E3-EU.

White boxes indicate features already part of the original model. Grey boxes indicate features not part of the core nor the updated model. Dark yellow boxes indicate the features that will be, and light-yellow boxes features that might be (still to be decided), explicitly developed for GEMINI-E3-EU in the DIAMOND project, and which are not in the core version of the model. Note that detailed market coverage in GEMINI-E3 is not included in the figure.

3.5 From NEMESIS to NEMESIS-World

The NEMESIS model (New Econometric Model of Evaluation by Sectoral Interdependency and Supply) is a sectoral detailed macroeconomic model for the European Union (Boitier et al. 2018). It is a system of economic models for every European country (including the United Kingdom), devoted to study issues that link economic development, competitiveness, employment and public accounts to economic policies, and notably all structural policies involving long term effects. The essential purpose of the model is to provide a consolidated framework to realise "Business As Usual" (BAU) scenarios (or other alternative scenarios), up to 30 to 40 years, and to assess the socioeconomic impact of the implementation of all additional policies not already implemented in the BAU. The main mechanisms of the model are based on the behaviour of representative agents: firms, households, government and rest of the world. From the supply side, the model distinguishes 30 different economic activities that produce goods and services through production functions and, to do so, uses production factors: capital, energy, low and high-qualified labour and other intermediate consumption. All these economic activities are interrelated by inter-sectoral exchanges (conversion matrices) and external trades with other EU countries and the rest of the world. NEMESIS includes a detailed energy-environment module that allows the model to deal with climate mitigation policies, at an EU and Member State level. This module enhances the representation of the energy system of each Member State by detailing the energy used (ten different products) by each economic activity but also by households. It also details the power generation sector by allocating electricity production between different technologies through diffusion curves. CO₂ emissions from fossil fuel combustion (FFC) are then calculated from fossil fuel consumption whereas other GHGs (CO₂ from other sources, CH₄, N₂O, HFCs, PFCs and SF₆) are either calculated by other modelled sectors or calibrated on external studies. Furthermore, the model can be relatively easily linked to other tools. In case of a linkage with more detailed energy-system models, NEMESIS is then used to assess the socioeconomic impacts at EU and Member State level, with the energy system modelling being delegated to the detailed energy models.

The development of the NEMESIS model will consist of the construction of a new model, called NEMESIS-World that will rely on the conceptual modelling approach of the current version of the NEMESIS model, that is a highly detailed macro-sectoral model for the Member States of the EU (+ UK, Norway and Iceland). The ambition of the NEMESIS-World model is to be the first open-source, global, large-scale, macro-economic model. The general structure of the model will be grounded on the mechanisms of the NEMESIS model. As the work is a step-by-step process, we cannot go now into the precise detail of the modelling. We plan to follow these different steps:

- Identifying model requirements in terms of coverage by individualising the largest economies and GHG emitters, and the selection of relevant economic activities for economy-energy-climate impact assessment. We will take stock of existing data to build the NEMESIS-World dataset, while the objective is to be able to include from 15 to 25 individualised countries/regions in the model (see **Error! Reference source not found.** for tentative regional disaggregation) covering a large part of global GHG emissions, GDP and population.
- Taking stock of existing dataset on macro, macro-sector, energy (see **Error! Reference source not found.**), environment and emissions detailed data (MRIO datasets, OECD, etc.) to build a consolidated dataset that will be used by the model. Data collection will also be conducted to improve input assumptions and calibrate the modelling parameters.
- Model validation will be based on responses to a set of benchmark scenarios, such as exogenous shocks on key drivers and standard mitigation simulations. All necessary information will be included in the model's documentation (data and parameters sources, equations, baseline procedure etc.)

- NEMESIS-World will also include some developments on the modelling of the labour market(s) in order to better understand the challenges and risks that the climate transition places on the labour supply and demand.
- As the model will be global, we will include a synthetic climate module to be able to assess the impact of emissions on the global/regional temperature change. Furthermore, we will introduce damages from climate change (e.g., see van der Wijst et al., 2023) either considering global/regional damage functions or some sector-specific impacts (coastal area, crops yields, etc.).

Figure 9. Regional disaggregation in NEMESIS-World

Yellow-to-red colours represent the regional groups that are explicitly disaggregated for this model. White-to-blue regions represent model regional groups that were part of the original model.

Figure 10. Summary of the resource, technology, and end-use demand representation in NEMESIS-World.

White boxes indicate features already part of the original model. Grey boxes indicate features not part of the core nor the updated model. Dark yellow boxes indicate the features that will be, and light-yellow boxes features that might be (still to be decided), explicitly developed for NEMESIS-World in the DIAMOND project, and which are not in the core version of the model.

3.6 From PROMETHEUS to OPEN-PROM

PROMETHEUS is a global energy system model covering in detail the complex interactions between energy demand, supply and energy prices at the regional and global level. Its main objectives are to: 1) assess climate change mitigation pathways and low-emission development strategies for the medium and long-term; 2) analyse the energy system, economic and emission implications of a wide spectrum of energy and climate policy measures, differentiated by region and sector; 3) explore the economics of fossil fuel production and quantify the impacts of climate policies on the evolution of global energy prices. The PROMETHEUS model provides detailed projections of energy demand, supply, power generation mix, energy-related carbon emissions, energy prices and energy system costs. PROMETHEUS is a fully-fledged energy demand and supply simulation model aiming at addressing energy system analysis, energy price projections, power generation planning and climate change mitigation policies. PROMETHEUS contains relations and/or exogenous variables for all the main quantities, which are of interest in the context of general energy systems analysis. These include demographic and economic activity indicators, primary and final energy consumption by main fuel, fuel resources and prices, CO₂ emissions, greenhouse gases concentrations and technology dynamics (for power generation, road transport, hydrogen production and industrial and residential end-use technologies). PROMETHEUS quantifies CO₂ emissions and incorporates environmental-oriented emission abatement technologies like renewable energy sources (RES), electric vehicles, CCS, and energy efficiency, as well as policy instruments, such as taxation, subsidies, and technology standards. The latter include both market-based instruments such as cap and trade systems differentiated per region and sector-specific policies and measures focusing on specific carbon emitting activities. Key characteristics of the model, that are particularly pertinent for performing the analysis of the implications of alternative climate abatement scenarios, include world supply/demand resolution for determining the prices of internationally traded fuels and technology dynamics mechanisms for simulating spill-over effects for technological improvements (increased uptake of a new technology in one part of the world leads to improvements through learning by experience which eventually benefits the energy systems in other parts of the World). PROMETHEUS is designed to provide medium- and long-term energy system projections and system restructuring up to 2050, both in the demand and the supply sides. The model produces analytical quantitative results in the form of detailed energy balances in the period 2015 to 2050 annually.

This task will develop the advanced version of PROMETHEUS (OPEN-PROM) with improved spatiotemporal, technology, and sectoral granularity. The model will be structurally enhanced by expanding its regional resolution (from 10 to more than 50 regions/countries, focusing on major emitters and EU countries, see **Error! Reference source not found.**); time horizon (from 2050 to 2100 with annual time steps); sectoral coverage (various industrial subsectors, building types, transport modes including international shipping and aviation); and technology representation (to include new mitigation options required for the transition to net zero, like hydrogen, synthetic e-fuels, BECCS, DAC, advanced biofuels, and CCUS, see **Error! Reference source not found.**). These enhancements will be underpinned by the development of a comprehensive database, ensuring consistency between various datasets related to energy system, emissions, technology data, and policies. Current representation of fossil fuel production and trade will be expanded to simulate trade in new clean energy forms (e.g., hydrogen, synthetic fuels) to allow the analysis of geopolitical implications of the transition to net zero. The

model will also be expanded to incorporate abatement cost-supply curves for all major non-CO₂ gases by region.

Figure 11. Regional disaggregation in OPEN-PROM.

Yellow-to-red colours represent the regional groups that are explicitly disaggregated for this model. White-to-blue regions represent model regional groups that were part of the original model or slightly updated multi-country aggregations.

Figure 12. Summary of the resource, technology, and end-use demand representation in OPEN-PROM.

White boxes indicate features already part of the original model. Grey boxes indicate features not part of the core nor the updated model. Dark yellow boxes indicate the features that will be, and light-yellow boxes features that might be (still to be decided), explicitly developed for OPEN-PROM in the DIAMOND project, and which are not in the core version of the model.

3.7 Interconnections with other models

In order to expand the capabilities of the six IAMs within the consortium, in WP4 they will be linked with additional bottom-up or higher resolution tools:

- GCAM-Europe, OMNIA, NEMESIS-World, and OPEN-PROM will incorporate **circular economy** assumptions by connecting with the “*Environmental Global Applied General Equilibrium*” (ENGAGE) model. The consideration of circularity, material efficiency, and recycling/secondary production potentials and costs will be particularly relevant for some sectors (e.g., industry), to assess the potential role of circular economy in deep decarbonisation pathways in the EU and other major economies.
- OMNIA and OPEN-PROM will be connected to the “*Model of Agricultural Production and its Impact on the Environment (MAgPie)*” a global land use allocation model, in order to include **land use dynamics and emissions**.
- GCAM-Europe, GEMINI-E3-EU, and OPEN-PROM (and, potentially, OMNIA and NEMESIS-World) will also be expanded to incorporate **household heterogeneity**. Based on bottom-up tools, such as microsimulation models (*CHANCE*) or the “*Fully Interregional Dynamic Econometric Long-term Input-Output (FIDELIO)*” model, IAMs will be enhanced to represent end-use consumer demands (e.g., food, transport, buildings) for alternative socioeconomic groups that can include income groups (i.e., deciles), urban/rural categorization, gender, or behavioural profiles. The incorporation of this feature will also allow the modelling teams to evaluate the “within-region” distributional impacts attributable to climate policies.
- OMNIA, CLEWS-EU, NEMESIS-World, and GEMINI-E3-EU will be connected to simple climate models (SCMs) such as “*CICERO-SCM*” to estimate the **climate impacts** (e.g., radiative forcing or temperature increase) associated with the alternative scenarios. The interlinkages between these models will also allow to analyse the effects of changing precipitation and temperature patterns on land productivity and the energy sector, and broader feedbacks of climate impacts for the economy.
- All the models will also be expanded to enhance their representation of their **labour and financial modules**, which is particularly important for the development of alternative technological pathways in a transition to a carbon neutral economy. Some of the planned improvements include the representation of the labour dynamics, or the regional differentiation of access to capital and/or financing costs (e.g., Weighted Average Cost of Capital, WACCs).
- GCAM-Europe, OMNIA, CLEWS-EU, and GEMINI-E3-EU will incorporate **behavioural aspects and preferences** to better represent the potential responses to alternative climate policies. Some of the most critical aspect to be explored will be the willingness/reluctance to lifestyle changes, such as potential modal shifts in passenger transport, or the transition to healthier, sustainable diets.
- GCAM-Europe, OMNIA, and OPEN-PROM will be connected to the *openTEPES* model to enhance their **representation of the electricity system**. The aspects to be improved include the finer temporal resolution (increasing the number of sub-annual time-segments), the dynamics to separate long-term decisions about capacity and short-term decisions about dispatching, or the endogenization of the investments for grid expansion.

The planned connections across the models are summarized in **Error! Reference source not found.**

Table 3. Summary of the planned inter-model connections associated with WP4

Model	Area	GCAM-Europe	OMNIA	CLEWS-EU	GEMINI-E3-EU	NEMESIS-World	OPEN-PROM
ENGAGE	Circular economy modelling						
MagPie	Agriculture and Land-Use modelling						
CHANCE/FIDELIO	Household heterogeneity -- private consumption module						
Open simple climate models (e.g., CICERO-SCM)	Climate and physical impacts						
-	Labour and Finance						
-	Behavioural change						
openTEPES	Detailed electricity system						

The yellow colour indicates the inter-model connections with WP4, whereas the brown colour indicates that the connections are still under discussion.

3.8 Policies and measures

This section explores the climate policies (**Error! Reference source not found.**) and broader energy, land and demand-side measures (**Error! Reference source not found.**) that could be represented with the updated models in the consortium. The implementation of the different policies into the different models is relevant for WP5, which focuses on exploration of alternative scenarios.

Considering that IAMs are explicitly designed to analyse the effects and impacts associated with alternative climate policies, the original version of the models within DIAMOND are already able to directly represent a suite of climate policies without any further modification (dark green in **Error! Reference source not found.**), such as carbon prices, emission quotas, climate targets, energy tax/subsidies, or land protection policies. Likewise, these models are usually flexible, so that additional policies could be implemented with some adjustments or modifications (light green). However, the updated and expanded model versions developed during the course of DIAMOND will expand the range of policies that can be implemented in the models. While the strategy to implement some of these new policies have already been established in some models (in dark yellow), some of these options require further planning so they still need to be decided (in light yellow). Note that some models will not represent the full range of policy options shown in the table (in white).

Table 4. Overview of the climate policies represented in each model.

Category	Policy measure	GCAM-Europe	OMNIA	CLEWS-EU	GEMINI-E3-EU	NEMESIS-World	OPEN-PROM
Emissions mitigation	Tax						
	Emissions target / quota						
	Regulations (emissions standards, etc...)						
	Global Temperature / Radiative Forcing target						
	Financial supports (negative emissions, CDMs, Green Climate Fund)						
Energy	Tax						
	Subsidy						
	Energy mix target						

Category	Policy measure	GCAM-Europe	OMNIA	CLEWS-EU	GEMINI-E3-EU	NEMESIS-World	OPEN-PROM
	Efficiency target						
	Regulations (thermal regulation in buildings, banning of diesel cars in urban areas, etc...)						
Land	Protected lands						
	Production quotas						
	Carbon sink pricing / Land use change emissions tax						
	Afforestation targets						
Trade	Carbon border tax on imports						
	Carbon border supports on exports						
	Regulations policies (certifications, Best-available technologies, standards, etc...)						
Policy not applicable in original or updated model	Policies that could be directly implemented in the original model version	Policies that could be implemented with the original version of the model, but with some modifications	Policy is planned to be represented in the updated model version	Option to implement the policy in the updated model version, but it still needs to be decided			

In addition, IAMs can also represent a wide range of economy-wide measures that are essential in a transition towards a carbon neutral economy. These measures include the use of cleaner or more efficient fuels or technologies in different end-use sectors (buildings, industry, transport, and agriculture), or additional mitigation options such as direct air capture, afforestation, or behavioural changes. The original models can also represent some of these options either endogenously (in green in **Error! Reference source not found.**) or exogenously (in blue). The updated model versions developed in this project will improve the representation of these measures in two ways: 1) incorporating the dynamics that were missing in the original version of the model; and 2) endogenizing some of the exogenous responses for a better representation of the real market dynamics. The development of these new features has been already decided (in dark yellow) or it is still pending (in light yellow). Similarly, some of the dynamics will not be represented in some models (in white).

Table 5. Overview of the energy, land and end-use demand measures represented in each model.

Category	Policy measure	GCAM-Europe	OMNIA	CLEWS-EU	GEMINI-E3-EU	NEMESIS-World	OPEN-PROM
Buildings	Fuel switch/energy mix						
	Technology substitution						
	Efficiency improvement						
Industry	Fuel switch/energy mix						
	Technology substitution						
	Efficiency improvement						
	CCS						
Combined heat and power	Fuel switch/energy mix						
	Technology substitution						
	Efficiency improvement						
	CCS						
Transport	Fuel switch/energy mix						
	Technology substitution						
	Efficiency improvement						

Category	Policy measure	GCAM-Europe	OMNIA	CLEWS-EU	GEMINI-E3-EU	NEMESIS-World	OPEN-PROM
	Modal shifts						
Agriculture	Fuel switch/energy mix						
	Technology substitution						
	Efficiency improvement						
	Land practices						
	Agroforestry						
	Animal husbandry practices						
Direct Air Capture	Direct Air Capture						
Land Use, Land-Use Change and Forestry (LULUCF)	Afforestation						
Behavioural Changes	Behavioural Changes						
The measure is not represented in the original or updated model version	The measure is represented endogenously in the original model version	The measure is exogenous in the original version of the model	The measure is planned to be incorporated or endogenized in the updated version of the model	The representation or endogenization of the measure in the original model version needs to be decided			

Bibliography

- Battiston, S., Monasterolo, I., Riahi, K., & van Ruijven, B. J. (2021). Krueger. *Science*, 372(6545), 918–920.
- Beck, M., & Krueger, T. (2016). The epistemic, ethical, and political dimensions of uncertainty in integrated assessment modeling. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Climate Change*, 7(5), 627–645.
- Beltramo, A., Ramos, E. P., Taliotis, C., Howells, M., & Usher, W. (2021). The global least-cost user-friendly CLEWs open-source exploratory model. *Environmental Modelling & Software*, 143, 105091.
- Binsted, M., Iyer, G., Patel, P., Graham, N., Ou, Y., Khan, Z., Kholod, N., Narayan, K., Hejazi, M., & Kim, S. (2021). GCAM-USA v5. 3_water_dispatch: Integrated modeling of subnational US energy, water, and land systems within a global framework. *Geoscientific Model Development Discussions*, 1–39.
- Byers, E., Krey, V., Kriegler, E., Riahi, K., Schaeffer, R., Kikstra, J., Lamboll, R., Nicholls, Z., Sandstad, M., & Smith, C. (2022). *AR6 scenarios database*.
- Dagnachew, A. G., Poblete-Cazenave, M., Pachauri, S., Hof, A. F., van Ruijven, B., & van Vuuren, D. P. (2020). Integrating energy access, efficiency and renewable energy policies in Sub-Saharan Africa: A model-based analysis. *Environmental Research Letters*.
- Emmerling, J., & Tavoni, M. (2021). Representing inequalities in integrated assessment modeling of climate change. *One Earth*, 4(2), Article 2.
- Galende-Sánchez, E., & Sorman, A. H. (2021). From consultation toward co-production in science and policy: A critical systematic review of participatory climate and energy initiatives. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 73, 101907.
- Giarola, S., Mittal, S., Vielle, M., Perdana, S., Campagnolo, L., Delpiazzo, E., Bui, H., Kraavi, A. A., Kolpakov, A., & Sognaes, I. (2021). Challenges in the harmonisation of global integrated assessment models: A comprehensive methodology to reduce model response heterogeneity. *Science of the Total Environment*, 783, 146861.
- Gidden, M. J., & Huppmann, D. (2019). pyam: A Python Package for the Analysis and Visualization of Models of the Interaction of Climate, Human, and Environmental Systems. *Journal of Open Source Software*, 4(33), 1095.

- Guivarch, C., Le Gallic, T., Bauer, N., Fragkos, P., Huppmann, D., Jaxa-Rozen, M., Keppo, I., Kriegler, E., Krisztin, T., & Marangoni, G. (2022). Using large ensembles of climate change mitigation scenarios for robust insights. *Nature Climate Change*, *12*(5), 428–435.
- Horowitz, R., Binsted, M., Browning, M., Fawcett, A., Henly, C., Hultman, N., McFarland, J., & McJeon, H. (2022). The energy system transformation needed to achieve the US long-term strategy. *Joule*, *6*(7), 1357–1362.
- Howells, M., Rogner, H., Strachan, N., Heaps, C., Huntington, H., Kypreos, S., Hughes, A., Silveira, S., DeCarolis, J., & Bazillian, M. (2011). OSeMOSYS: the open source energy modeling system: An introduction to its ethos, structure and development. *Energy Policy*, *39*(10), 5850–5870.
- Huppmann, D., Rogelj, J., Kriegler, E., Krey, V., & Riahi, K. (2018). A new scenario resource for integrated 1.5 C research. *Nature Climate Change*, *8*(12), 1027–1030.
- IPCC. (2022). *Climate Change 2022: Mitigation of Climate Change. Contribution of Working Group III to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change [P.R. Shukla, J. Skea, R. Slade, A. Al Khourdajie, R. van Diemen, D. McCollum, M. Pathak, S. Some, P. Vyas, R. Fradera, M. Belkacemi, A. Hasija, G. Lisboa, S. Luz, J. Malley, (eds.)]*. Cambridge University Press. Cambridge, UK and New York, NY, USA. doi: 10.1017/9781009157926
- Keppo, I., Butnar, I., Bauer, N., Caspani, M., Edelenbosch, O., Emmerling, J., Fragkos, P., Guivarch, C., Harmsen, M., & Lefevre, J. (2021). Exploring the possibility space: Taking stock of the diverse capabilities and gaps in integrated assessment models. *Environmental Research Letters*, *16*(5), Article 5.
- Krey, V., Guo, F., Kolp, P., Zhou, W., Schaeffer, R., Awasthy, A., Bertram, C., de Boer, H.-S., Fragkos, P., Fujimori, S., He, C., Iyer, G., Keramidas, K., Köberle, A. C., Oshiro, K., Reis, L. A., Shoai-Tehrani, B., Vishwanathan, S., Capros, P., ... van Vuuren, D. P. (2019). Looking under the hood: A comparison of techno-economic assumptions across national and global integrated assessment models. *Energy*, *172*, 1254–1267. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2018.12.131>
- Loulou, R., & Labriet, M. (2007). ETSAP-TIAM: The TIMES integrated assessment model Part I: Model structure. *Comput. Manag. Sci*, *5*(1–2), 7–40.
- Miller, C. A., & Wyborn, C. (2020). Co-production in global sustainability: Histories and theories. *Environmental*

Science & Policy, 113, 88–95.

- Mulugetta, Y., Sokona, Y., Trotter, P. A., Fankhauser, S., Omukuti, J., Somavilla Croxatto, L., Steffen, B., Tesfamichael, M., Abraham, E., & Adam, J.-P. (2022). Africa needs context-relevant evidence to shape its clean energy future. *Nature Energy*, 1–8.
- Nikas, A., Gambhir, A., & Boitier, B. (2023). *Promoting sustainable transitions across the globe. Special Issue in Renewable and Sustainable Energy Transition*.
- Nikas, A., Skalidakis, S., Sorman, A. H., Galende-Sanchez, E., Koasidis, K., Serepas, F., Van de Ven, D.-J., Moreno, J., Karamaneas, A., & Koutsellis, T. (2021). *Integrating integrated assessment modelling in support of the Paris Agreement: The I2AM PARIS platform*. 1–8.
- O'Neill, B. C., Kriegler, E., Riahi, K., Ebi, K. L., Hallegatte, S., Carter, T. R., Mathur, R., & van Vuuren, D. P. (2014). A new scenario framework for climate change research: The concept of shared socioeconomic pathways. *Climatic Change*, 122(3), Article 3. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-013-0905-2>
- Peng, W., Iyer, G., Bosetti, V., Chaturvedi, V., Edmonds, J., Fawcett, A. A., Hallegatte, S., Victor, D. G., van Vuuren, D., & Weyant, J. (2021). *Climate policy models need to get real about people—Here's how*.
- Pindyck, R. S. (2013). Climate change policy: What do the models tell us? *Journal of Economic Literature*, 51(3), 860–872.
- Pindyck, R. S. (2017). The use and misuse of models for climate policy. *Review of Environmental Economics and Policy*.
- Poblete-Cazenave, M., Pachauri, S., Byers, E., Mastrucci, A., & Van Ruijven, B. (2021). Global scenarios of household access to modern energy services. *Nature Energy*.
- Rao, N. D., van Ruijven, B. J., Riahi, K., & Bosetti, V. (2017). Improving poverty and inequality modelling in climate research. *Nature Climate Change*, 7(12), Article 12.
- Robertson, S. (2021). Transparency, trust, and integrated assessment models: An ethical consideration for the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Climate Change*, 12(1), e679.
- Rosen, R. A. (2015). IAMs and peer review. *Nature Climate Change*, 5(5), 390–390.
- Sampedro, J. (2021). Accounting for access and inequality. *Nature Energy*, 6(8), Article 8.

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-021-00872-z>

- Sampedro, J., Iyer, G., Msangi, S., Waldhoff, S., Hejazi, M., & Edmonds, J. A. (2022). Implications of different income distributions for future residential energy demand in the US. *Environmental Research Letters*, 17(1), Article 1.
- Skea, J., Shukla, P., Al Khourdajie, A., & McCollum, D. (2021). Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change: Transparency and integrated assessment modeling. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Climate Change*, 12(5), e727.
- Sognaes, I., Gambhir, A., van de Ven, D.-J., Nikas, A., Anger-Kraavi, A., Bui, H., Campagnolo, L., Delpiazzi, E., Doukas, H., & Giarola, S. (2021). A multi-model analysis of long-term emissions and warming implications of current mitigation efforts. *Nature Climate Change*, 11(12), Article 12.
- United Nations. (2008). *International Standard Industrial Classification of All Economic Activities—Statistical Papers* (Sales No. E.03.XVII.4, No.4, Rev.31).
- UNFCCC (2016). *Just transition of the workforce, and the creation of decent work and quality jobs*. FCCC/TP/2016/7. UNFCCC.
- van Beek, L., Hajer, M., Pelzer, P., van Vuuren, D., & Cassen, C. (2020). Anticipating futures through models: The rise of Integrated Assessment Modelling in the climate science-policy interface since 1970. *Global Environmental Change*, 65, 102191.
- Van der Sluijs, J. P. (2002). A way out of the credibility crisis of models used in integrated environmental assessment. *Futures*, 34(2), 133–146.
- van der Wijst, K.-I., Bosello, F., Dasgupta, S., Drouet, L., Emmerling, J., Hof, A., Leimbach, M., Parrado, R., Piontek, F., Standardi, G., & van Vuuren, D. (2023). New damage curves and multimodel analysis suggest lower optimal temperature. *Nature Climate Change*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-023-01636-1>
- Van Ruijven, B. J., O'Neill, B. C., & Chateau, J. (2015). Methods for including income distribution in global CGE models for long-term climate change research. *Energy Economics*, 51, 530–543.
- Weyant, J. (2017). Some contributions of integrated assessment models of global climate change. *Review of Environmental Economics and Policy*.

Wise, M., Patel, P., Khan, Z., Kim, S. H., Hejazi, M., & Iyer, G. (2019). Representing power sector detail and flexibility in a multi-sector model. *Energy Strategy Reviews*, 26, 100411.

Zhang, Y., Binsted, M., Iyer, G., Kim, S., Wild, T., & Zhao, M. (2022). Long-term basin-scale hydropower expansion under alternative scenarios in a global multisector model. *Environmental Research Letters*, 17(11), 114029.

ANNEX

Model documentation survey

The surveys with the information on the IAMs, including their regional, sectoral, policy coverage, as well as the calibration data and input assumptions are publicly available on Zenodo here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7774836>

